

Decoding the symbolism in the Art Deco heritage structures of Mumbai

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Abstract

On June 30, 2018, UNESCO declared the Victorian Gothic and Art Deco ensembles of Mumbai (the capital of Maharashtra), to be a UNESCO World Heritage Site. With around 200 such structures dotting the city, Mumbai boasts of the second largest concentration of such sites after Miami. The heritage status was the result of concerted efforts for close to a decade by urban planners, heritage activists, local residential groups, and architects. The unique Art Deco style of architecture emerged thanks to large-scale migration to Bombay (as the city was called then) and reclamation of 439.6 acres of land in the 1920s under the Backbay Reclamation Scheme. The initial Art Deco structures would be set up from the 1930s. The Art Deco movement brought about a significant shift from the colonial Neo-Gothic/Victorian Gothic prototype in terms of architecture. Art Deco architecture reflected aspects of cosmopolitanism, the city's origins as a seaport, the quest for modernity and multiculturalism -- traits that still characterise the maximum city. This paper explores the various motifs visible on Art Deco structures of the city and the symbolism inherent in them. For this research paper, we have relied on external secondary data accessed via books, research papers, and online resources.

Keywords

Art Deco, Heritage, Architecture, Symbolism, Conservation, Bombay, Mumbai, Maharashtra, Urban Planning, UNESCO World Heritage site

Introduction

In 2018, the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) inscribed Mumbai's Victorian Gothic and Art Deco Ensembles as a World Heritage Site. It was the most recent addition to the list for the state of Maharashtra, which boasts of several other heritage sites such as the Ajanta and Ellora Caves, Elephanta Caves, and the Chhatrapati Shivaji Terminus. The 2018 World Heritage Site status was the result of a decade-long campaign led by resident associations, heritage activists, urban planners, conservationists, and architects. While the heritage site tag was bestowed on the Art Deco structures located in the areas spanning Marine Drive and Oval Maidan, we can also find such structures scattered across areas in Matunga, Dadar, Bandra and Chembur.

The Art Deco style of architecture was originally applied on tracts of reclaimed land as part of the Backbay Reclamation Scheme in the 1920s, which identified 439.6 acres of reclaimed land for construction.

This style of architecture in Bombay (as the city was formerly called) was preceded by the Neo-Gothic/Victorian Gothic and Indo-Saracenic style of architecture.

In this paper, we explore the symbolism associated with Art Deco structures in the city. For the purpose of research, we have relied on secondary data collected from online archives, newspapers, research papers, and books.

What is Art Deco?

Historically, Art Deco design emerged with a legendary 1925 government-sponsored exposition in Paris, and remained in vogue internationally from 1919 to 1939. The term 'Art Deco' came to be coined only in 1968 as scholars were looking to reassess the style. The term Art Deco is an abbreviation of the French term 'Arts Decoratifs'. Initially, this style of architecture was referred to as "le style moderne" or "Jazz Moderne".

Art Deco emerged during the period after the First World War and right before the Second World War. The motifs that predominantly featured in Art Deco structures included the preoccupations of the time including technological progress, consumerism and making strides towards modernity.

Art Deco designs are characterised by geometric shapes, streamlining, use of pastel colours, ziggurats, and nautical elements. While Neo-Gothic structures were made from igneous basalt and soft limestone, Art Deco structures were made using steel frames, opaque glass, terracotta, smooth-faced stone, plaster, and reinforced cement concrete (RCC).

What made this style of architecture unique was the fact that it amalgamated diverse influences and movements including Western modernism, Jazz music, Cubism, Egyptian architecture, Bauhaus, Ballets Russes, and Futurism.

Architecturally, Neo-Gothic structures which preceded the Art Deco structures featured buttresses, turrets, gargoyles, vaulted arches, and pointed rooflines which symbolised a reverence for a mighty imperial power.

Art Deco structures in Bombay, in contrast, made a strong nationalistic statement against colonial rule by incorporating indigenous motifs that symbolised the local people's industriousness, multiculturalism, cosmopolitanism, pragmatism, and functionalism.

Art Deco buildings encompassed cinemas (Regal, Eros, Metro), residential spaces (Rajjab Mahal, Soona Mahal, Empress Court), offices (New India Assurance building, Lakshmi Insurance building), and hospitals (Breach Candy Hospital, Dr Purandare Maternity and Gynaecological Hospital).

While Art Deco architecture in Bombay ushered in a new design sensibility, it retained an Indian-ness in its overall character. The architects were Indians who

trained in European styles of architecture (in India or abroad) and applied their knowledge in a modern style that suited indigenous sensibilities and conditions.

Symbolism in Art Deco architecture

Symbolism, in plain terms, refers to the use of symbols to represent ideas. In architecture, it can refer to the expressive connotation of a structure. As Rudolph Arnheim states in *The Dynamics of Architectural Form* (1977), “A work of architecture, as a whole and in its parts, acts as a symbolic statement, which makes humanly relevant qualities and situations evident through our senses.”

Symbolism need not be veiled or indecipherable since it is based on elements that are familiar to us. As Arnheim further explained, “The symbolism of the arts, of which architecture is the most important, could not be so effective, it could not move us so profoundly and prevail over changes in cultural convention if it were not rooted in the strongest human experiences, available to everybody from infancy.”

Art Deco design, with its focus on minimalism and geometric designs, forged a new paradigm which broke away from the larger-than-life Neo-Gothic motifs. It was an apt template for designing emerging architectural spaces.

Here are some instances of symbolism that are evident in Art Deco structures in the city:

a) Art Deco structures featured modern stylized lettering for the building name signs. As public opinion turned against colonial rule, there emerged a trend of naming structures using Indian names, such as Bharatiya Bhavan and Keval Mahal. The use of scripts also shifted from Latin to Hindi, Urdu and Gujarati.

A wave of nationalism is also evident in the form of indigenous cultural motifs such as lotuses, images of Goddess Lakshmi, elephant sculptures and characters of the farmer and potter.

Art Deco can even be construed as “a form of resistance and as a backdrop of the freedom movement”, as stated by Dr Mustansir Dalvi in his paper *Expressions of Modernity: Semiotic Isotopy on Bombay’s Backbay Reclamation Buildings* (2015).

Even the use of RCC in construction was a political statement of sorts, as it reflected “India’s ability to independently industrialise” (Baral 2019).

b) The initial constructions were mainly built to accommodate the elite moneyed class consisting of merchants, industrialists and Indian princes. The Hindu symbols of prosperity like statues of goddess Lakshmi reflect a desire for prosperity and commercial success. Other auspicious Hindu symbols like the ‘Om’ are also evident in some structures.

Even classical Egyptian elements, such as hieroglyphs and sphinxes, featured on some structures were a nod to the newly-discovered tomb of Tutankhamen in 1922, and the riches that emerged from it.

c) Even though Art Deco structures were part of an ensemble and had to contend with height restrictions, each structure reflected something unique in terms of colour, typography or design. Eros Cinema is a case in point. It incorporates a ziggurat-like tower to add an illusion of height and of standing tall amidst other structures in the Churchgate area.

d) The Bombay of those times was evolving swiftly in terms of technology and modes of transport. The Art Deco structures reflect the design sensibility of ocean liners, airplanes, and locomotives through rounded locomotive balconies, streamlining, and porthole windows.

Nautical themes of waves, observatory towers, and ship-deck style railings also reflected the uniqueness of Mumbai as a port city.

e) Other common motifs were of the sunburst and the frozen fountain. Both images symbolize eternal life. The frozen fountain was revived by French designer Rene Lalique, whose designs at the 1925 Paris Exposition gave impetus to the Art Deco style.

f) The city's multiple cultures also got represented in the diversity of Hindu, Islamic, and Zoroastrian motifs on structures which were inspired by different religious groups that coexisted peacefully in the city.

Summary

The Art Deco movement influenced the architecture of Bombay and gave it a unique creative expression. Art Deco structures were highly functional and reflected the aspirations of a rapidly developing society. The predominant Art Deco motifs encapsulated modernity, cohabitation, dynamism, and an appreciation of the milieu and the roots of the people living/working in/passing through the structures. It remains an index and cultural marker of a city that is still associated with the very values that this style of architecture epitomises.

* ***Disclaimer:*** *Mumbai is referred to as Bombay in some parts of the paper as it was the earlier name of the city in the period we are referring to.*

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